

Long list of possible dimensions and characteristics to classify collaborative sessions to enable support artefact tailoring

1st version (i.e., after initial brainstorming):

The Ws	Dimension (neutral, <i>not conclusive</i>)	Exemplary (<i>not conclusive</i>) characteristics	Dimension (modeling-flavored, potentially other characteristics)
How	Used software types	Presentation, business intelligence, ...	Model embeddedness
How	Climate	Trust, mistrust	N/A
How	Structure	Structured, unstructured	N/A
How	Participation mode	Mainly frontal presentation, mainly discussion	Degree of collaboration possible
What	Topic focus	Focus on {strategy processes & roles IT}, no focus	Topic to be modeled
What	Focal artefact	Document, presentation, ...	Model embeddedness
When	Duration	< 1 hour, 1-2 hours, > 4 hours, > 1 day	Time for developing / comprehending models
When	Number of occurrences	High, low	'Amortization potential' of modeling effort
When	Mode of occurrence	Regular, iterative	'Amortization potential' of modeling effort
When	Trigger	Stakeholder-initiated, prescribed	N/A
Where	Place	Onsite, offsite	N/A
Where	Participant distribution	Virtual, in-person, hybrid	Degree of collaboration possible
Who	Number of stakeholders involved	< 5, 5-10, 10-50, >50	N/A
Who	Stakeholders / management levels involved	Operational, tactical, strategic	Experience with modeling; attention level
Who	Stakeholder familiarity	Familiarity, no familiarity	N/A

The Ws	Dimension (neutral, <i>not conclusive</i>)	Exemplary (<i>not conclusive</i>) characteristics	Dimension (modeling-flavored, potentially other characteristics)
Who	Power distribution	Symmetric, asymmetric	N/A
Who	Information distribution	Symmetric, asymmetric	N/A
Why	Success	Objectives reached, objectives missed	N/A
Why	Mode of thinking	Convergence, divergence	[Part of] Alternatives
Why	Decision type	Identification of alternatives, selection of alternatives	[Part of] Alternatives
What	Completeness of relationships between all entities of the same type	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Completeness of relationships between all entities of different types	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Importance of a characterization of the entities discussed	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Completeness of entities discussed (of a specific type)	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Importance of thinking about alternatives / variants	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Heterogeneity of the entity types relevant for the session	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Level of granularity for discussing the entities	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Coherency	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Consistency (within / between models)	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Consistency (concerning the internal environment)	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>
What	Consistency (concerning the external environment)	Important, not important	<i>See left</i>

2nd version (i.e., after eliminating dimensions for which no direct relation to modeling could be established, then assessment of the remaining ones):

Dimension (modeling-flavored)	Common theme	Sessions: exemplary (<i>not conclusive</i>) characteristics	Support artefacts: exemplary (<i>not conclusive</i>) characteristics	Relevant?	Differentiated?	Clear?	Informative?	Independent?	Simple?	Stable?	Count of +
Time for developing / comprehending models	Appropriateness for sophisticated modeling	Few, much	Modeling effort high, modeling effort low				+	+	+		3
'Amortization potential' of modeling effort	Appropriateness for sophisticated modeling	Model reused often, model not reused often	Modeling effort high, modeling effort low	+			+	+		+	4
Model embeddedness	Appropriateness for sophisticated modeling	Dedicated modeling software used, graphical editor used, no graphical software used	Dedicated modeling software required, graphical editor required, no graphical software required		+	+	+		+		4
Experience with modeling	Appropriateness for sophisticated modeling	Experience existing, no experience existing	Complex method, simple method		+		+		+		3
Attention level	Appropriateness for sophisticated modeling	High with all participants, high with some participants, not existing	Complex method, simple method		+				+	+	3
Degree of collaboration possible	Appropriateness for sophisticated modeling	Much collaboration possible, little collaboration possible	N/A				+		+		2
Topic to be modeled	Information characteristics	Focus on {strategy processes & roles IT}, no focus	Focus on {strategy processes & roles IT}, no focus				+	+	+	+	4

Dimension (modeling-flavored)	Common theme	Sessions: exemplary (<i>not conclusive</i>) characteristics	Support artefacts: exemplary (<i>not conclusive</i>) characteristics	Relevant?	Differentiated?	Clear?	Informative?	Independent?	Simple?	Stable?	Count of +
Completeness of relationships between all entities of the same type	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+	+	+		+	+	6
Completeness of relationships between all entities of different types	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+	+	+		+	+	6
Importance of a characterization of the entities discussed	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	7
Completeness of entities discussed (of a specific type)	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	7
Importance of thinking about alternatives / variants	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	7
Heterogeneity of focal entity types	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	7
Level of granularity for discussing the entities	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+	+	+		+	+	6
Coherency	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+	+		+			+	4
Consistency (within / between models)	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+						+	2
Consistency (concerning the internal environment)	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+						+	2
Consistency (concerning the external environment)	Information characteristics	Important, not important	Supported, not supported	+						+	2